

Research Paper

Artificial Intelligence Innovations and Election Administration in Nigeria

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Abstract

There is an urgent need for Nigeria to continue leading the way in the adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies for improving election administration amid ongoing electoral reforms. This paper explores the contributions of emerging AI innovations to election administration in Nigeria. Specifically, it examines the current state of election administration, reviews existing literature on AI applications in electoral processes, and identifies potential areas where AI can strengthen election management. Data on the possible applications of AI innovations were collected through a survey of 396 Nigerian voters, electoral stakeholders, and election administrators. The findings reveal that AI has significant potential to enhance election administration by improving fraud detection, strengthening transparency, increasing operational efficiency, and promoting the integrity of the electoral process. However, the study also identifies implementation challenges relating to technological infrastructure, public trust, and institutional readiness. The study concludes that the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) should progressively adopt AI-driven technologies to reduce electoral fraud and corruption while enhancing the credibility, transparency, and effectiveness of elections in Nigeria.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Election Administration, Electoral Process, Innovation, Nigeria

1. Introduction

A key element of democratic governance is election administration, whose success or failure can determine whether election results are legitimate or not. African Election Management Bodies' (EMBs') digital transformation is a top goal in this direction. With digital transformation initiatives still in their infancy, majority of EMBs still use antiquated manual systems. Their capacity to fully utilize AI for election management is hampered by the underdeveloped digital infrastructure (European Think Tanks Group, 2024). The use of technology in the conduct of elections has generated heated debate from scholars, policymakers, and the public in Africa. The use of technology has brought doubts and fears towards the election system in Nigeria and Africa, unlike the rest of the world, where it remains an indispensable aspect of credibility, integrity, trust, transparency, and fairness (Obalum, Nwosu & Ananti, 2024).

Technology adoption has played an important role in the overall electoral process as nations continue to ensure that result of the election is an encapsulation of the fundamental values of democracy (Adelaja, 2023; Ogunyemi, 2023; Odote & Kanyinga, 2021). In Nigeria and Africa, the population, the polity, and the academia had different stands towards the use of technology in elections. Unlike the rest of the world, where technology adoption remains an indispensable aspect of credibility, integrity, trust, transparency, and justice, technology usage in Nigeria and Africa triggered doubts and fears towards the election system (David, Adeniyi & Aliu, 2024).

1.1. Statement of the Problem

Electoral processes in Nigeria still faces several issues such as vote rigging, manipulation of results, impersonation of voters, misinformation, cyber attacks, and loss of faith in the outcome of elections. Although technological advances have been growing all over the world, the implementation of AI technology in the election management of Nigeria is yet to receive proper attention. Previous studies have mostly focused on technology and very few studies have explored the use of AI to prevent electoral

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fraud and protect the integrity of elections. Hence, there has been insufficient knowledge about how much people are aware of and accepting the use of AI innovations for managing election problems in Nigeria.

1.2. Research Questions

Based on the problems identified in this paper, the following research questions were asked:

1. What is the level of awareness of AI in election administration in Nigeria?
2. What AI technologies are perceived as useful for election fraud prevention in Nigeria?
3. How effective are AI-driven measures in detecting and preventing election fraud in Nigeria?
4. What challenges hinder the implementation of AI in election security and fraud prevention in Nigeria?

1.3. Research objectives

This study aimed at examining the role of AI innovations in enhancing election administration and fraud prevention in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

1. Examine the level of awareness of AI in election administration in Nigeria
2. Identify AI technologies useful for election fraud prevention
3. Assess respondents' perception of election fraud and AI detection measures
4. Investigate challenges facing the implementation of AI in election security in Nigeria.

2. Review of Literature

Artificial Intelligence (AI) was first consummated in 1956 by prominent American computer scientists McCarthy, Minsky, Rochester, and Shannon, as the science and engineering of making intelligent machines like the intelligent computer programs. In the twenty-first century, artificial intelligence (AI) has become a key technological force that has the potential to significantly affect international relations (Amaresh, 2020); a machine-based system that can make predictions, recommendations, or decisions influencing real or virtual environments for a given set of human-defined objectives, (OECD AI Principles, 2023); a replication of human intellect in robots that are made to mimic human behaviour and thought patterns (Frankenfield, 2022). AI has also been applied to computers that have been programmed to exhibit traits of the human mind, including perception, reasoning, learning, problem-solving, planning, control, and prediction (Kha, 2023; Liang, Wang & Tang, 2025).

Artificial intelligence (AI) is academically defined as the capability of computer systems to perform tasks that typically require human intelligence, such as reasoning, decision-making, and autonomous action. It is understood through three main approaches: AI as an intelligent entity, AI as autonomous

machines capable of rational and empathetic action, and AI as engineered systems designed by professionals.

In their study on “Artificial Intelligence and Public Management and Governance in Developed and Developing Market Economies”, Agba, Agba, and Obeten (2023) looked at how public management and governance in developed and emerging economies relate to AI. The study concluded that there are lots of untapped potentials in the interaction between AI and public administration. They also recommended that further study should be done and that professionals and specialists who are interested in incorporating AI into more useful facets of public administration and governance be given additional assistance.

The use of AI in the management of elections has drawn numerous studies. The use of AI-based chatbots for the purposes of educating the voters and engaging them was contemplated by the International Foundation for Electoral Systems (IFES). The European University Institute also researched the use of AI to detect and prevent the manipulation of elections. The use of technology in the management of elections, e.g., the voting machines and the voters’ register platforms, has also been researched in Nigeria (International Foundation for Electoral systems (IFES, 2026).

Many scholars have commented on the challenges Nigeria faces with its voting technology deployment. Electoral technology effectiveness in facilitating elections has been hampered by low internet and broadband connectivity. There were also concerns over the electoral commission’s logistical preparedness, poor planning, and implementation, which have undermined effective technology application. Doubts were raised about the voting process’s integrity and security due to Nigeria’s poor information infrastructure on cybersecurity, which rendered the electoral process vulnerable to attacks by hackers (Ifeanyi-Ajufo & Hoffman, 2023).

Lack of confidence in the electoral process, worsened by incumbent political establishment’s co-opting of election administration institutions, has undermined both the implementation of electoral technology and public trust in it (Peter & Inokoba, 2024).

Election technology, according to the argument by Maurer (2020), consists of technological solutions used to manage the democratic challenges involved when holding elections. Based on the argument by Maurer, it is clear that electoral technology involves a wide range of “digital solutions” used throughout the election cycle, such as voting, registering, and collating, among others. Most stakeholders (voters, political parties, election management bodies, and the media) utilise digital technologies on multiple levels of the election cycle. Biometric technology, blockchain technology, cloud computing technology, and artificial intelligence technology are digital technologies being studied.

Electoral technology involves the use of biometric technologies such as fingerprints and facial recognition technology to ensure the accreditation of the voters, credible results, and the effectiveness of the election management bodies to avoid fraudulence and other malpractices impacting credibility (Ogunyemi, 2023). Integrating technology into African elections marked a significant step toward curbing human interference in manipulating electoral outcomes. The increasing use of technical innovations in African elections, such as optical scanners, biometric technology, and other electronic gadgets, enhanced

the credibility, safety, and transparency of the electoral process in several African countries Cheeseman et al. (2018). Jacobsen (2019) observed that the conduct of free, fair, and credible elections in Africa has often been undermined by violence, manipulation, and systemic rigging. In response to these persistent challenges, he argued that the continent's adoption of electoral technology became a crucial intervention, helping to restore trust in both institutions and the electoral referee. By enhancing the transparency of electoral processes, safeguarding integrity, and reinforcing public confidence, electoral technology continues to deliver significant advantages to the democratic experience in Africa.

Although there is little doubt that electoral technology would alleviate some problems that the electoral democracy faces in the continent. Angalapu (2023) noted that lack of confidence among citizens towards the electoral body continues to exist. He went on to say that electoral technology in Nigeria has made it easier for people to register to vote and is a key element in encouraging young people who were disappointed with the results of the last elections in Nigeria to run for the presidency in 2023. Yeboah (2023) pointed out that the ability of the electoral umpires to adopt electoral technologies effectively and the quality of their execution would continue to be important factors during elections. Fatai (2023) noted that the electoral system has eradicated certain election irregularities.

2.1. Theoretical Framework

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) created by Davis (1989) is used as the foundation of this study. The theory describes the acceptance and use of new technologies by users by its perceived usefulness and ease of use. TAM is well applicable to the understanding of the perception of stakeholders on AI to improve electoral transparency, electoral fraud and election security in Nigeria, especially within an election administration context. It is theorized that the adoption of AI-powered technologies like biometric verification, automated result collation, surveillance and misinformation detection will be influenced by how users trust the technologies' effectiveness and reliability. The theoretical underpinning of this study, therefore, is the application of the TAM which provides a theoretical basis for the study of the effect of awareness, trust, perceived efficiency of AI innovations on their adoption in election administration and electoral fraud prevention in Nigeria.

3. Methodology

This study adopts a descriptive survey research design, suitable for assessing perceptions, knowledge, and attitudes toward AI applications in election fraud prevention. The target population includes Nigerian electoral officers, cybersecurity specialists, political scientists, ICT specialists, security personnel, and ordinary citizens in the list of voters across six geopolitical zones in Nigeria.

Purposive sampling was used to select participants who have experience or knowledge related to electoral processes and artificial intelligence. For representativeness of the sample, participants were drawn across the six geopolitical regions of Nigeria where a state is selected per geopolitical zone for representativeness. These States are Kaduna (Northwest), Adamawa (Northeast), Ogun (Southwest), Abuja (Northcentral), Abia (Southeast), and Edo (Southsouth). These areas were purposively selected

to represent Nigeria's six geo-political zones and capture regional variations in electoral experiences, political participation, and technology adoption. The selected states have also experienced notable electoral challenges, making them suitable for examining the role of AI in election fraud prevention and electoral integrity.

Table 1. Variables Measurements.

Objectives	Variables/Indicators	Measurement Scale
Examine the level of awareness of AI in election administration	Awareness of AI applications in elections; Knowledge of AI in fraud prevention	Yes/No; Low–High Scale
Identify AI technologies useful for election fraud prevention	Biometric verification, AI surveillance, cybersecurity tools, automated result collation, misinformation detection	Multiple Response Scale
Assess perceptions of election fraud and AI detection measures	Severity of election fraud; Effectiveness of AI detection measures	Ordinal Scale; 5-point Likert Scale
Investigate challenges affecting AI implementation in election security	High cost, technical expertise, political resistance, cybersecurity risks, poor digital infrastructure	5-point Likert Scale

Source: Authors Computation

A total of 480 questionnaires were distributed across the selected States, with 396 valid responses returned, representing 82.5% response rate, considered adequate and reliable for statistical analysis and generalisation of findings.

Data were analysed using descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentages, while Chi-square analysis was employed to examine respondents' perception and associations among variables at 5% level of significance using Statistical Package for Social Sciences, version 26.

4. Data Presentation/Analysis

4.1. Awareness and Knowledge of AI in Elections

Findings from Table 2 revealed relatively high awareness by respondents about the utilization of AI in election management. In this regard, 66.7% were aware of the use of AI in election processes, while 33.3% did not have any awareness about it. It was evident from the statistical test of significance for the Chi-square test ($\chi^2 = 44.000$, $p = .000$) that there was a significant difference between the respondents' levels of awareness. As far as knowledge of AI applications in preventing election fraud is concerned, 62.1% of the participants had moderate knowledge, 21.2% of them had low knowledge, and 16.7% of them had high knowledge about the use of AI in managing elections. The large Chi-square value ($\chi^2 = 148.909$, $p = .000$) implies that respondents showed considerable variation in their understanding of AI applications. From all the AI technologies mentioned, the most useful one

Table 2. Analysis of Respondents’ Opinion on Awareness and Knowledge of AI in Elections.

Items	Response	f	%	Chi-square Test
Aware of artificial intelligence (AI) applications in election administration	Yes	264	66.7	44.000 [1] (0.000)
	No	132	33.3	
	Total	396	100.0	
Knowledge of AI in preventing election fraud	Low	84	21.2	148.909 [2] (0.000)
	Moderate	246	62.1	
	High	66	16.7	
	Total	396	100.0	
Which AI technologies do you think are most useful in election fraud prevention?	Biometric verification (fingerprint, facial recognition)	54	13.6	24.909 [4] (0.000)
	AI-powered surveillance (CCTV analytics, drone monitoring)	84	21.2	
	Misinformation detection (fake news and deepfake analysis)	72	18.2	
	Cybersecurity tools (intrusion detection, vote encryption)	72	18.2	
	Automated result collation and fraud detection	114	28.8	
	Total	396	100.0	

Figures in [] and () represent degrees of freedom and p-values, respectively.
 Source: Authors’ Field Survey Data, 2025.

according to the responses was automation of result collation and fraud detection (28.8%). Surveillance systems accounted for 21.2%, and cybersecurity/misinformation detection, as well as biometrics, 18.2% and 13.6% respectively.

4.2. Analysis of Respondents’ Opinion on Election Fraud and AI Detection Measures

Table 3. Significance Test of Election Fraud and AI Detection Measures.

Election Fraud and Detection Measures	Chi-Square	df	p-value
How significant do you think election fraud is in Nigeria?	257.818	3	0.0000
What forms of election fraud do you think AI can help mitigate?	90.545	5	0.0000
AI-powered biometric verification can prevent voter identity fraud?	406.727	4	0.0000
How effective do you think AI-powered surveillance (CCTV, drones) would be in detecting election malpractices?	370.545	3	0.0000
AI-driven fraud detection in election result collation would enhance electoral integrity	217.636	4	0.0000
AI help in detecting and preventing misinformation and deep fake content during elections	217.636	4	0.0000

Source: Authors’ Field Survey Data, 2025.

Figure 1. Graphical Representation of Respondents’ Opinion on Election Fraud and Detection Measures.

Source: Researchers’ Field Survey Data, 2025.

The findings in Table 3 revealed that election fraud is widely perceived as a serious challenge in Nigeria’s electoral system. Out of the 396 respondents, 57.6% considered election fraud a major problem, while 25.8% viewed it as a moderate issue. Only 16.7% perceived it as either a minor or non-existent problem. The Chi-square result ($\chi^2 = 257.818, p = 0.000$) indicates that the observed differences are statistically significant.

Concerning the forms of election fraud that artificial intelligence (AI) could help mitigate, respondents identified electoral result manipulation (28.8%) and cyber-attacks on election systems (25.8%)

as the major areas where AI could be most beneficial. Ballot box stuffing and misinformation dissemination accounted for 13.6% each, while multiple voting and voter impersonation represented 12.1% and 6.1% respectively. The significant Chi-square value ($\chi^2 = 90.545$, $p = 0.000$) further confirms the relevance of these perceptions.

Respondents also expressed strong confidence in the effectiveness of AI-driven election security measures as shown in Figure 1. A combined 89.4% agreed that biometric authentication could effectively prevent voter identity fraud, while 65.2% considered AI-powered surveillance technologies such as CCTV and drone monitoring highly effective in detecting electoral malpractices. Furthermore, 74.2% believed that AI-driven fraud detection during result collation would enhance electoral integrity, while similar proportions supported the use of AI in combating misinformation and deepfake content during elections. All the variables examined recorded statistically significant Chi-square values ($p = 0.000$), indicating strong respondent consensus regarding the usefulness of AI technologies in improving election administration and fraud prevention in Nigeria.

Table 4. Analysis of Respondents' Opinion on the Challenges Faced in the Implementation of AI for Election Security and Fraud Prevention.

Items	SD	D	N	A	SA	Total	Chi-square
High implementation cost	6 (1.6%)	12 (3.1%)	12 (3.1%)	204 (53.1%)	150 (39.1%)	384 (100.0%)	455.063 [4] (0.000)
Lack of technical expertise	6 (1.6%)	0 (0.0%)	6 (1.6%)	240 (62.5%)	132 (34.4%)	384 (100.0%)	398.250 [3] (0.000)
Resistance from political stakeholders	24 (6.3%)	18 (4.7%)	30 (7.8%)	198 (51.6%)	114 (29.7%)	384 (100.0%)	319.125 [4] (0.000)
Cybersecurity risks	0 (0.0%)	6 (1.6%)	24 (6.3%)	216 (56.3%)	138 (35.9%)	384 (100.0%)	306.760 [3] (0.000)
Poor digital infrastructure	24 (6.1%)	18 (4.5%)	60 (15.2%)	168 (42.4%)	126 (31.8%)	396 (100.0%)	217.636 [4] (0.000)

Source: Researchers' Field Survey Data, 2025.

Table 4 shows the perceptions of the participants on the barriers that pose challenges to the use of AI in securing Nigerian elections. The results indicate an overwhelming consensus among the respondents regarding the difficulties associated with the implementation of AI for election security. These challenges include the high cost of implementation, inadequate technical expertise, resistance from political stakeholders, cybersecurity risks, and poor digital infrastructure. All the identified challenges recorded statistically significant Chi-square values ($p < 0.001$), indicating that respondents strongly agreed that these factors constitute major barriers to the successful implementation of AI for election security and fraud prevention in Nigeria.

5. Discussion of Findings

From the research results, it is evident that a considerable percentage (66.7%) of the respondents indicated that they were aware of the utilization of AI technologies in the election process, implying an

increased awareness of technological advancements in Nigeria's electoral system. Nevertheless, despite the high levels of awareness, a few (16.7%) were knowledgeable about how AI can be used to mitigate election fraud, while many (62.1%) had moderate knowledge on the topic. The result is consistent with International IDEA (2024) assertions that even though public interest in using AI in elections is growing across the world, literacy rates on how it works are still low, especially in developing democracies.

In terms of useful technologies for reducing fraud in elections, respondents ranked automated result collation and fraud detection (28.8%), surveillance technology (21.2%), and cybersecurity technologies (18.2%) as the top three. The results agreed with the view by Brennan Center for Justice (2023) that cybersecurity technologies, surveillance, and result collation are the best AI applications in securing election information and ensuring smooth election processes. Moreover, the use of AI-driven surveillance technologies such as facial recognition and drone monitoring in monitoring polling units during elections is widespread in some democracies (Okoye, 2024).

Election fraud was considered a serious problem in Nigeria by most respondents, with 57.6% indicating that it is one of the prominent problems. Electoral result manipulation (28.8%), cyber-attack (25.8%), misinformation (13.6%), and ballot box stuffing (13.6%) were ranked as the electoral frauds to be addressed through AI technology. According to Esiefarienrhe (2024), the integration of AI technologies would be most effective in ensuring the transparency of electoral results and offering protection against cyber-attacks. Similar sentiments were echoed by Odiawa (2024), who highlighted the importance of combating deepfake content and misinformation in enhancing electoral trust.

It is worth noting that respondents had high confidence in various AI technologies. For instance, 89.4% agreed or strongly agreed that biometric technology would eliminate voter identity fraud, 65.2% viewed AI-driven surveillance technology as highly effective in exposing electoral fraud, and 74.2% believed that AI-based fraud detection technology would significantly improve election integrity. This was consistent with the use of biometric technology in India and the digital voting systems implemented in Estonia (IDEA, 2024).

In spite of the high level of confidence, several barriers were identified. Most (92.2%, 96.9%, and 92.2%) agreed that the high cost of implementation, lack of technical know-how, and cybersecurity risks are the major impediments to adopting AI in election management. The results agreed with the observations by Brennan Center for Justice (2023) that there are significant challenges, such as the high cost of implementing AI technology and the lack of technical capacity, which developing countries face when using AI in elections. Respondents reported political resistance (81.3%) and poor ICT infrastructure (74.2%) as other barriers, as observed by Odiawa (2024).

The implications of the study results suggest that there is increasing public confidence in the ability of AI technologies to transform the Nigerian electoral system positively, but institutional challenges impede their effective implementation. Thus, it is important for electoral officials to focus on capacity building and stakeholder sensitization, digital infrastructure development, and partnerships between the private and public sectors to ensure that the benefits of AI are realized. Without addressing the basic

conditions necessary for the successful implementation of AI, there might not be a revolution in the country's electoral system.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

Adopting the innovations of AI in the management of Nigerian elections would improve the electoral process, raise the confidence of the voters, and minimize the likelihood of violence and bloodshed. However, there are challenges that should be tackled. These include the need to introduce appropriate regulatory mechanisms, capacity building, and infrastructure development. Government needs to invest in the development of digital infrastructure, including cybersecurity infrastructure, cloud computing platforms, and data centres.

On capacity building, the Electoral Commission should introduce stakeholders and election managers to training programmes and initiatives aimed at improving their knowledge of AI-based election management solutions and the associated legal procedures. Furthermore, comprehensive regulations on data protection and privacy should be formulated to guide and control the application of AI technologies in election management, thereby ensuring transparency, accountability, and public trust in the electoral process.

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